

Thermal Characteristics and Prediction of Crystallization Kinetics of Nifedipine Using Calorimetric Study

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Presenting Author' Biography

Dr. Pravin Kumar Singh is an MSCA Post Doctoral Fellow at Institute of Advanced Materials, IAAM, Sweden. Before this fellowship, he served as a Group Leader at VBRI Innovation Centre, New Delhi, India. He was an assistant professor in physics at KIPM College of Engineering and Technology in Gorakhpur, India. Before that, he worked as a Guest Faculty in Madan Mohan Malaviya University of Technology, Gorakhpur, India for two years. Dr. Singh has a PhD in physics and two master's degrees, M.Sc. in electronics and communication and M.Tech in optoelectronics and laser technology. As per his research contributions, he has written a book and more than 50 papers that have been published in well-known international journals. He is Managing Editor of Advanced Materials Proceedings and reviewers in many high impacts reputed journals.

Graphical Abstract

Abstract

This study uses Differential Scanning Calorimetry to estimate the crystallization kinetics of Nifedipine, a common pharmaceutical drug. Due of its crystallization characteristic, nifedipine, which treats hypertension and angina, is difficult to formulate. Understanding and anticipating this behavior is essential for drug stability and efficacy. Nifedipine's thermal behavior is analyzed using DSC under controlled conditions. The study finds crystallization-related exothermic and endothermic activities by heating and chilling samples. The thermal signatures are utilized to create a kinetic model that predicts Nifedipine crystallisation in various pharmaceutical formulations. The model includes crystallization onset temperature, peak temperature, enthalpy changes, and cooling rate to explain crystallization kinetics. The study also examines how excipients and manufacturing processes affect Nifedipine crystallization, helping optimize formulation techniques. This research should improve the quality control and stability of Nifedipine-based drugs. The predictive model built using DSC analysis helps the pharmaceutical industry formulate and manufacture stable and effective therapeutic products by studying Nifedipine crystallisation behaviour.

Keywords: Nifedipine, API, Crystallization kinetics, DSC, thermal analysis.

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